

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE PERFORMANCE OF CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN INCLUSIVE SPECIAL SCHOOLS AND NON-INCLUSIVE SPECIAL SCHOOLS IN JOS NORTH, PLATEAU STATE

By

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Abstract

The thrust of this paper find out comparative study on English Language Performance of children with congenital hearing impairment in inclusive special school and non-inclusive special school in Jos North, Plateau State. The objective of the study was to compare the English Language performance of children with congenital hearing impairment in inclusive special school and those in non-inclusive special schools in Jos North. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.5 level of significance. Comparative research design was adopted. The population for this study was 32 children from inclusive special school and non-inclusive special school in Jos North. The sample size was 16 children with congenital hearing impairment in inclusive special school and those in non-inclusive special school in Jos North. Simple random sampling was used to select the sample. The instruments used for data collection was children academic records and teacher made achievement test on word recognition and reading comprehension. The data collected from the field was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using mean and percentages. Hypotheses were tested using t-test for independent samples. The result showed that children in inclusive special school demonstrated a remarkably higher in reading comprehension compared to their peers in non-inclusive special school. In word recognition, children in inclusive special school again outperformed those in non-inclusive special school. The overall academic performance across two terms showed that children in inclusive special school had a better performance compared to those in non-inclusive special school and the analysis revealed statistically significant differences in performance between the two groups across all measures. It is therefore recommended that the research has proven that the performance of primary three children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition in inclusive special school is better than those in non-inclusive special school settings. The research has provide insight on the fact that the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in reading comprehension and word recognition in inclusive special school is greater than those in non-inclusive special school in Jos North LGA.

Key Words: Children with Congenital Hearing Impairment, Inclusive Special Schools, Non-Inclusive Special Schools and English Language Performance.

Introduction

Education is the method of transforming a person into a responsible, purposeful, imaginative, artistic, and useful individual. It seeks to maximize an individual's inherent potentials so that he may be beneficial to himself and the community in which he finds himself. Inclusive education is a process of enhancing the capacity of the education system in any country to reach out to diverse children. The basis of inclusion is that special needs children have a right to the benefits of a full school experience, with needed modifications and supports, alongside their peers without disabilities who receive general education. Inclusions contend that special classes, separate schooling, or other forms of removing children with disabilities from regular environment should occur only when the nature or severity of the disability of the children is such that education in regular classes (with the use of supplementary services) cannot be accomplished. Today in Nigeria, special educators, parents of children with disabilities, policy-makers and other stakeholders continue to debate the benefits and challenges of this education paradigm (Ajuwon, 2008). The discussions have been shaped largely by the principle of inclusion which stresses that ordinary schools should cater to all children and young people, regardless of their circumstances or personal characteristics.

The concept of inclusive education is based on the fact that all children and young people, despite different cultural, social and learning backgrounds, should have equivalent learning opportunities in all kinds of schools. United Nations Education Society Cooperative Organization (2008) emphasizes that educational system schools and teachers should focus on general inclusive setting that uphold the values of respect and understanding of cultural, social and individual diversity. Essentially, inclusive education is an approach that looks into how to transform educational systems and other learning environment in other to respond to the diversity of children. Focusing on inclusive education and strategies that address the causes and consequences of discrimination, inequality and exclusion within the holistic framework of Education For All (EFA) goals. Collaboration and teamwork are also essential aspects of inclusive practice.

Lazarus and Ajibade (2012) reported that attempts have been made to actually integrate children with special needs into regular schools but this attempt was met with skepticism on the part of the teachers. This is a pointer that awareness for the implementation of inclusive education is a challenge even from the part of teachers. It has been stressed also that inclusive education in Nigeria is faced with the following challenges: Personnel preparation, lack of specialized curriculum, learning environment, funding, school management structures, pedagogy, condition of service, government policy, monitoring and evaluation, and inadequate instructional materials.

It is on this background that those who oppose such system vehemently profound that special residential school should be the best options for those who are living with special needs conditions. Children with special need cannot have proper academic achievement based on their abilities. In order to meet the needs of v with special needs in an inclusive programme the teacher has a lot of tasks at hand. Full implementation of policy and programme has not seen the light of the day and where inclusive education exist. Mwapishak (2017) opine that some parents do not want their normal children mix up with children who are living with special needs.

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Collaboration is the hallmark of effective special education. In today's inclusive special schools, special educators are expected to coordinate their work with that of other professionals, both within and outside the school including general educators, therapists, nurses, social workers, psychologists, counselors, and rehabilitation specialists (Ludlow, 2021). Ludlow added that these professionals engage in collaboration in areas such as assessment, identification of program and services, curriculum development, instructional delivery and service coordination with many different agencies. Teacher collaboration has been defined broadly by Friend and Cook in lingo, Barto-Arwood and Jolivette (2021) as a 'style direct interaction between at least-co-equal parties voluntarily engaged in shared decision making as they work toward a common goal'. There are multiple methods of teacher collaboration consultation, and collaborative problem solving (Brownell, Adams, Sindelar, Waldron, and Van-Hover, 2024). They explained that regardless of the model, the focus is on the teachers working together with an assumption that collaboration lead to improved children academic achievement.

Collaboration between special and general educators is not only essential but was documented in the U.S. 2004, Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act (IDEA, 2004) that mandates this collaboration. Special educators must form partnership with general educators to create inclusive special school environment for all children. In Nigeria, this collaboration between the special and general education teachers with other professionals cannot said to have started, but it addresses such issues as accountability, achievement and effective use of instructional materials.

The Cornell University (2016) stated that inclusive teaching strategies refer to a number of teaching approaches that addresses the needs of children with a variety of background, learning styles and abilities. They informed that the strategies contribute to an overall inclusive learning environment, in which children feel equally valued. The regular classroom teacher is the main implementer of inclusive education rest on the teacher to ensure that inclusive teaching strategies are employed to meet the diverse learning needs of all including childrenwith needs. When implemented properly, an inclusive classroom environment can help children with disabilities develop both cognitively and socially (Reinhart, 2012). Children have confirmed the following teaching strategies to be effective in teaching in inclusive classrooms. Ability grouping, remedial instruction, individualized instruction, co-operative learning strategy, enrichment, acceleration, differentiated instruction, Universal Design for Learning (UDL), utilization of variety of teaching strategies, pull-out programmes, team teaching, collaboration, some curriculum and modified goals, instructional accommodations, interaction or collaborative instructional approaches, teacher questions, class discussion, cooperative learning approach, peer tutoring and Brain-based instructional approach.

Babudoh and Ozoji (2012) observed that inclusive education is managed by professionals who are mainly teachers both regular and special teachers. It is imperative then to equip them though regular capacity building to prepare their mind on how best to adopt the new approach for quality access to education. The school structures that accommodates all children need to be rehabilitated and upgraded to meet inclusive learning surrounding which increase full participation and suitable learning experiences for all children. By implication, schools should be

more of resource based with all the supportive services available to consolidate for other unique children learning needs.

Hearing impairment means damage to the organ of hearing which consecutively gives rise to abnormal functioning of the auditory system. It is a decrease sensitivity of the human hearing due to the existing hurt or injury within the organ of hearing. Such decrease in auditory sensitivity is often seen as an abnormality (Ruscetta, 2015). Children with hearing impairment is one whose organ of hearing is injured or hurt and as a result; his/her hearing acuity is deviated from the societal norm (none or reduced/low hearing). Hearing impairment may be mild, moderate, severe or profound and may also depend on the onset of the hearing impairment. This impairment to the organ of hearing may be caused by ototoxic substances such as drugs, congenital factors and excessive exposure to noise. Others are trauma, syndrome, infection or other diseases. These sometimes result in malformation or malfunctioning of the organ of hearing. Hearing loss hampers this process and causes language disorder. Therefore, normal language acquisition in the hearing-impaired child requires special training based on the degree of hearing loss. Abiodun (2011) opines that, congenital hearing impairment is a condition where an individual was either born with a hearing impairment or became hearing impaired before meaningful language was acquired, which is also known as pre-lingual hearing impairment. The adventitiously hearing impaired child had access to mother tongue, therefore, had acquired some language skills before becoming hearing impaired, which is also branded as post-lingual hearing impairment. According to World Health Organization (2024), hearing impairment is associated with negative consequences such as apathy, fear of discrimination; fear of stigmatization seems to be the root cause of the said rejection. This eventually results in poor academic performance, which also or in turns results to psychological trauma/grief.

Thus, children with congenital hearing impairment refers to a condition or trait that is present at birth or acquired during prenatal development. Babudoh (2021) defined congenital hearing impairment as a condition where an individual was either born hearing impaired or became hearing impaired before meaningful language was acquired. Pre-lingual/ Congenital hearing impairment can range from mild to profound, and it may affect one or both ears. Children with congenital hearing impairment are learners who are either born with hearing impairment or became hearing impaired before acquisition of societal language. The causes of congenital hearing impairment can vary and include genetic factors, prenatal infections, and exposure to certain medications or substances during pregnancy, complications during birth, or other medical conditions. Children with congenital hearing impairment may have varying degrees of difficulty in perceiving, understanding, or producing spoken language due to their hearing loss. They may require accommodation and support to ensure effective communication and equal access to education. These accommodations can include the use of hearing aids, cochlear implants, assistive listening devices, sign language interpreters, captioning, note-taking assistance, and classroom modifications.

Academic performance is an outcome, achievement and the extent to which an academic exercise ends. Academic performance is simply an academic accomplishment; it is an effect of education the extent to which a children performs. All children (learners) are required to maintain a satisfactory academic record and meet the obligations of the subjects/courses in which they are

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enrolled. This includes how well or bad learners do in their academic work. Children with Hearing Impairment are learners in primary schools and are living with hearing impairment. Children academic performance plays a crucial role in producing the best quality leaders and manpower for the country (Ali, 2009).

Furthermore, academic performance of children with hearing Impairment (both the pre-lingual and post-lingual hearing impaired) are summarized thus: hearing impaired learners' achievement on the Stanford Achievement Test (SAT) is markedly depressed in spelling, vocabulary, English language performance and others, their performances often fall behind their hearing peers, in reading and English comprehension especially (Ojile, 2010). As of the time hearing impaired children enter elementary school, they are typically already well behind children with normal hearing in spoken English, reading and even in Signed Language. Their abilities in most school subjects are grossly deficient. Even the best hearing impaired children graduating from high schools demonstrates depressed achievement: scores in comparison to their hearing peers (Ojile, 2010). Ojile (2010) further opined that as of the time children with hearing impairment entered elementary school, they are typically already well behind children with normal hearing in spoken English, reading and even in sign language. Their ability in most school subjects are grossly deficient. Even the best children with hearing impairment graduating from high school demonstrates depress achievement: scores in comparison to their hearing peers because English is considered as the world lingua franca.

Reading comprehension is the process of decoding and understanding written or printed language symbols in order to derive meaning and comprehend the content of a text. It involves the interaction between the reader's prior knowledge, language skills, and the written text itself. When reading, individuals visually perceive and interpret the letters, words, sentences, and paragraphs on a page or screen. They use their knowledge of phonics (sound-letter relationships), vocabulary, grammar, and syntax to decode and understand the words and sentences in the text. This decoding process allows readers to recognize and assign meaning to the words they encounter. Reading comprehension according to McKee (2024) is the ability to understand a text, analyse the information, and interpret correctly what the writer has stated.

Children with hearing impairment performance in English language experience problems between what they read and comprehend. They often encounter serious problems in what they can express, compute, negotiate and communicate in English language. This growing gap often dislocates their processes of social interaction, teaching-learning and very importantly reading and comprehension. To understand many of the problems that children with hearing impairment face, there is need to examine the consequence that children with hearing impairment loss exerts on the victims' reading and comprehension and by implication, their general academics development.

Children with hearing impairment experience problems with reading and comprehension, often face great deprivation of essential services at school, at home and in the society at large. Rodda and Eleweke (2000) said that this can basically be considered as the root cause of their learning and developmental difficulties and the resulting limited proficiency in reading, English literacy and mathematical analysis or reasoning. The poor understanding of the children with hearing impairment in English language of children in schools is really a disturbing problem to

teachers, parents and the society at large, because it is difficult to predict exactly what children with congenital hearing are actually passing through in life and especially in learning and subsequently in their academic pursuits and general life achievement.

Word Recognitions; Word recognition enables children with hearing impairment to concentrate on the meaning of the text. Word recognition skills could be taught such that it enables the reader to recognize words by sight without paying attention to the individual letters that make up the words. Since reading comprehension is the ultimate goal in teaching children to read, a critical early objective is to ensure that they are able to read words with instant, automatic recognition. Word recognition skills enable children with hearing impairment to be aware of prints, recognize words and learn ways to consciously or unconsciously figure out and call out these words; that is, unlock unknown words, perhaps by decoding the printed words and letters and by matching letters and words with or without sounds. Word recognition enables children with hearing impairment to concentrate on the meaning of the text. As children with hearing impairment grow in learning it is expected that their word recognition also develops and increases in number. It is based on the above that the researcher seeks to examine English Language performance of children with congenital hearing impairment in inclusive special schools and non-inclusive special schools in Jos North.

Statement of the Problem

Children with hearing impairment struggle to acquire skills needed to become confident in English language and comprehend what they read to enable them construct simple sentence, read, write and comprehend texts, lack ability to phonetically break down written words and comprehend them. English language is considered to be a basic need in the modern world, many children in secondary schools lack sentence construction skills. Some children with hearing loss have dropped out of schools due to English language difficulties and without acquiring the necessary sentence construction which could be simple, sentence. They also have problem in comprehension and word recognition. Children with congenital hearing impairment most often, cannot express themselves satisfactorily.

Despite growing support for inclusive education, the optimal learning environment for deaf children in terms of sentence formation remains unclear. While inclusive special schools offer exposure to spoken language and social interaction with hearing peers, special schools provide specialized instruction and a strong deaf cultural identity. Studies have shown that children with congenital hearing impairment have not been performing very well in schools due to inadequate acquisition of language. The assumption as revealed by most literature reviewed showed that the poor performance might be caused by factors one of which is a method of teaching by Nigerian educators for children with hearing impairment which do not take into consideration the means of communication that will appeal to all the senses of children with hearing impairment.

Lack of English language skills often grossly affect their academics performance, therefore, preparing children with hearing loss adequately for sentence construction expertise should be seen as an essential part of the education of the children with hearing loss. Children with hearing loss have language problem there by construct sentence at a slower pace, spend

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more time understanding what they've say or read, and have less awareness of mistakes in comprehension compared to their hearing peers.

Reading comprehension is said to be a continuing concern for children with hearing loss. Hearing impaired globally often struggle with sentence construction comprehension and there is a need for implementing effective sentence construction strategies to improve English Language performance of children with congenital hearing loss. It is on the bases of this that the researchers wish to investigate comparative study on English Language performance of children with congenital hearing impairment in inclusive special schools and non-inclusive special schools in Jos North, Plateau State

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to carry out comparative study on English Language performance of children with congenital hearing impairment in inclusive special schools and non-inclusive special schools in Jos North, Plateau State. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition in inclusive and special school settings.
2. Determine the performance of primary (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in reading comprehension in inclusive and special school settings.

Research Question

1. What is the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition in inclusive and special school settings?
2. What is the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in reading comprehension in inclusive and special school settings?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the performance of primary (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition in inclusive and special school settings.
2. There is no significant difference in the performance of primary (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in reading comprehension in inclusive special school and non-inclusive special school settings.

Research Design

The research utilized a comparative research design. Comparative research design is a collection of facts, data and information from the respondents in non-inclusive special schools and inclusive special school at a single period of time. The choice of this design is based on time span needed to complete the study and it is also appropriate because it aid the researcher to collect first-hand information for the study.

Population

The population of the study comprised of one inclusive special schools and one non-inclusive special schools with a total of 32 children. Otana Integrated school Jos had 13 children and Islamiya Science Pilot School Jos had 21 children. All children are in primary three(3) with congenital hearing impairment in the two schools within Jos North Local Government: Otana Integrated school Jos and Islamiya Science Pilot School Jos.

Sample is a scientific process in which a part of a population is selected in a manner or way that are sure it can be taken to represent that population from which it has been drawn in a research study. The sample for this study was taken from one inclusive special school (Otana Integrated School Jos) and one non-inclusive Special School Jos (Islamiya Science Pilot School Jos) with a total numbers of 8 children from each of the selected schools Therefore, the sample size was 16 children with congenital hearing impairment in primary three (3).

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A random selection between Islamiya Pilot School as non-inclusive school in Jos North LGA and Otana Integrated School Jos as an inclusive special school were selected among other inclusive special schools and non-inclusive special school in Jos North LGA.

INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The instruments used for data collection was children Academic Records (CAR) and Teacher Made Achievement Test (TMAT) on word recognition and reading comprehension. The word recognition and reading comprehension were extracted from a passage from the children text book which has exercises on word recognition and reading comprehension.

Description of Instruments

Children Academic Records (CAR). The Children Academic Records on performance English language for two terms was obtained from the school record. The cumulative achievement scores for each children for two terms were obtained from each children file. The achievement scores were collated to get the mean (\bar{x}) for each children. This was done for all the children both in the non-inclusive special schools and inclusive special school.

Teacher Made Achievement Test (TMAT).

Teacher Made Achievement Test (TMAT) was used in this research for data collection assessing the performance of the children in the two types of schools that is in non-inclusive Special School and inclusive special schools. The Teacher Made Achievement Test (TMAT) was in four sections. Sections A elicit information from the respondents about their personal data such as: sex, age and class. Sections B. measured the participant's reading comprehension. Sections C on word recognition. Specifically the teacher made test was made up of a short story with comprehension questions, exercise reading comprehension and word recognition exercise.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

Validity

The instruments used for this study was subjected to content validity by experts in the Department of Special Education and Rehabilitation Sciences, Faculty of Education, University of Jos in order to strengthen their relevance. The measures taken to validate the instruments include: subjecting the instrument together with the purpose, to the expert from department of educational foundations and special education and rehabilitation science for scrutiny.

Reliability

Reliability shows the degree to which an instrument is consistent in measuring whatever it measures. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, it was subjected to a test-retest analysis and the reliability index was 0.80. The instrument was used on two children from Dominionium Integrated School Jos, twice within two weeks interval.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the field was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using mean and percentages. Hypotheses were tested using t-test for independent samples. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 was used.

Results

Research Question One

What is the Performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition in Non-inclusive Special School and inclusive special school setting?

Table 1: The performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition from non-inclusive Special School and inclusive special school.

Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Non inclusive Special school	Inclusive Special school
1	40	70
2	45	66
3	50	80
4	38	70
5	55	68
6	42	75
7	36	80
8	50	70
Mean (\bar{x})	44.5000	72.3750
Std deviation	6.67618	5.34355

Table 1: Presents the performance of JSS II children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition, comparing those from special schools and inclusive special schools. The table shows that both groups consist of eight children each. The table indicated the lowest score in word recognition in special school was 36% and the highest score was 59%. It also shows that the lowest score in word recognition in inclusive special school was 66% and the highest score in inclusive special school was 80%. The table specifically indicated that the mean (\bar{x}) score on word recognition in special school was 44.5% with a standard deviation (SD) of 6.67. While the mean (\bar{x}) score in inclusive special school was 72% with a standard deviation of 5.34%. This indicated that children in inclusive special school are performing much better in word recognition than those in special school.

Research Question 2: What is the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital learning impairment in reading comprehension in inclusive and special school settings?

Table 2: Performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment from special and inclusive non inclusive special schools in reading comprehension.

S/N	Non Inclusive School	Special Inclusive school
1	40	72
2	38	68
3	42	70
4	35	60
5	50	70
6	40	76
7	41	60
8	46	65
Mean (\bar{x})	41.50	67.6
Std deviation	4.66	5.655

Table 2 shows that each school consist of eight children the table indicated that the lowest score in reading comprehension from non-inclusive special schools was 35% and the highest score was 50%. Similarly the lowest score in reading comprehension from inclusive non-inclusive special schools was 60% and the highest score was 79%. The table clearly indicated that the mean (\bar{x}) score on reading comprehension from non-inclusive special schools as 41.50% with a standard deviation (SD) of 4.66. Whereas the mean (\bar{x}) score from inclusive special school as 67.63% with a standard deviation (SD) of 5.65. This posits that the inclusive special school environment may provide more effective support for children with congenital hearing impairment. Leading to better performance in reading comprehension.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in word recognition.

Table 3. Test analysis on word recognition of primary three (3) children from non-inclusive special schools and inclusive special school

S/N	Type of school	No	Mean (x)	SD	d.f	T	P. value	α
1	Non-Inclusive Special Schools	8	44.500	6.67	7	18.853	000	0.05
2	Inclusive special school	8	72.37	5.34	7	38.309	000	0.05

Table 3 shows the comparison on performance in word recognitions between non-inclusive special schools and inclusive special school. The mean (x) score in the special school was 44.500% while that of inclusive special school was 72.37% the t-calculated for non-inclusive special schools was 18.853 while for inclusive special school was 38.309 and the p. value was 000. Since the p. value was less than 0.05 it means that the research has to reject the null hypothesis. This mean that there is significant difference in the performance of JS 2 children (with congenital hearing impairment) in word recognitions between learners in non-inclusive special schools and those inclusive special schools, in favour of those in inclusive special schools.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in reading comprehension.

Table 4: Test analysis on reading comprehension of primary three (3) children from non-inclusive special schools and inclusive special school.

S/N	Type of school	No	Mean (x)	SD	d.f	t	P. value	α
1	Special school	8	41.500	4.66	7	25.190	000	0.05
2	Inclusive special school	8	67.62	5.65	7	33.822	000	0.05

Table 4 shows the comparison on performance in reading comprehension between non-inclusive special schools and inclusive special school. The mean (x) score in the special school was 41.500% while that of inclusive special school was 67.62% the t-calculated for special school was 25.190 while for inclusive special school was 33.822 and the p. value was 000. Since the p. value was less than 0.05 it means that the research has to reject the null hypothesis. This mean that there is significant difference in the performance of primary three (3) children (with congenital hearing impairment) in reading

comprehension between learners in non-inclusive special schools and those inclusive special schools, in favour of those in inclusive special schools.

DISCUSSION

Based on the finding of the study, it revealed that in research question one shows that both groups consists of eight children each. The table indicated the lowest score in word recognition in special school was 36% and the highest score was 59%. It also shows that the lowest score in word recognition in inclusive special school as 66% and the highest score in inclusive special school as 80%. It indicated that the mean (\bar{x}) score on word recognition in special school was 44.5% with a standard deviation (SD) of 6.67. While the mean (\bar{x}) score in inclusive special school was 72% with a standard deviation of 5.34%. This indicated that children in inclusive special school are performing much better in word recognition than those in special school. This finding is consistent with international research, such as that by McLeskey and Waldron (2015), which found that inclusive classrooms promote better literacy outcomes due to the collaborative learning environment and access to a broader range of resources. In Nigeria, the work of Eze (2021) also supports these findings, indicating that inclusive education enhances word recognition skills among children with disabilities. Eze's research highlights the importance of integrating assistive technologies and differentiated instruction in inclusive settings, which may contribute to the improved performance observed in this study.

Research question two shows that each school consist of eight children the table indicated that the lowest score in reading comprehension from special school was 35% and the highest score was 50%. Similarly the lowest score in reading comprehension from inclusive special school was 60% and the highest score was 79%. The table clearly indicated that the mean (\bar{x}) score on reading comprehension from special school as 41.50% with a standard deviation (SD) of 4.66. Whereas the mean (\bar{x}) score from inclusive special school as 67.63% with a standard deviation (SD) of 5.65. This posits that the inclusive special school environment may provide more effective support for children with congenital hearing impairment. Leading to better performance in reading comprehension. Reading comprehension involves higher-order cognitive processes such as inference making, integration of prior knowledge, and syntactic parsing.

The superior performance of children in inclusive special schools may be attributed to increased opportunities for collaborative learning, peer modeling, and use of multimodal instructional strategies, which enhance comprehension. These learning environments possibly provide more scaffolding techniques, such as guided reading, think-aloud strategies, and visual aids, all of which are conducive to improving the comprehension skills of deaf learners. The result aligns with that of Ojile (2010) who reported that children with hearing impairment typically struggle with comprehension but perform better when instruction is adapted to their specific linguistic needs. Furthermore,

it is possible that inclusive settings promote social constructivist learning principles where learners build understanding through interaction with more capable peers. This form of situated learning could be particularly beneficial for deaf childrens, offering them meaningful contexts in which language is both modeled and practiced.

Summary of Findings

After the analysis, the findings reveals that:

1. Reading Comprehension: children in inclusive special schools demonstrated a remarkably higher in reading comprehension compared to their peers in non-special school.
2. Word Recognition: In word recognition, children in inclusive special schools again outperformed those in special schools. The results highlight the advantages of inclusive education in developing essential language skills.
3. Overall Academic Performance: The overall academic performance across two terms showed that children in inclusive special schools had a better performance compared to those in special schools. This further emphasizes the positive impact of inclusive educational practices on the academic outcomes of children with congenital hearing impairment.

Conclusion

From the result of the findings, it showed that performance of primary three (3) children with congenital hearing impairment in English language skills specifically reading comprehension, sentence construction, and word recognition between inclusive special schools and special schools differs. Based on that, it is here conclude that children in inclusive special schools significantly outperformed their peers in special schools across all measured areas. The performance in English language indicated that inclusive educational environments provide more effective support and resources, leading to enhanced language skills and overall academic performance. The statistical significance of the results underscores the importance of inclusive education in fostering better educational outcomes for children with congenital hearing impairment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Promotion of Inclusive Education: Educational authorities should promote and expand inclusive education programs that integrate children with congenital hearing impairment into mainstream classrooms. This approach do not only benefits the children with congenital hearing impairment but also enriches the learning environment for all children.

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2. **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** It is essential to provide ongoing training and professional development for teachers in inclusive settings. Educators should be equipped with the skills and strategies necessary to effectively support children with hearing impairments, including differentiated instruction and the use of assistive technologies.
3. **Resource Allocation:** Schools should ensure that adequate resources, such as teaching materials, assistive devices, and support staff, are available in inclusive classrooms. This will help create a conducive learning environment that meets the diverse needs of all children.
4. **Parental Involvement:** Schools should encourage and facilitate parental involvement in the education of children with congenital hearing impairment. Engaging parents in the educational process can enhance children motivation and reinforce learning at home.
5. **Policy Development:** Policymakers should develop and implement policies that support inclusive education initiatives, ensuring that children with disabilities have equal access to quality education. This includes establishing guidelines for the inclusion of children with hearing impairments in mainstream classrooms. Educational stakeholders can work towards creating a more inclusive and supportive educational environment that enhances the academic performance and overall well-being of children with congenital hearing impairment by implementing these recommendations.

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